

Metal Complex Formations by Bromopyrogallol Sulphonphthalein

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Bromopyrogallol sulphonphthalein (BPR), which behaves similar to the dyes of hydroxytriphenylmethane class, has widely been employed as an analytical reagent¹ based on the formation of coloured complexes with metals². In the investigations on complex equilibria consisting the ligand, metal ions and the complex species reported earlier³, the coordinating behaviour of all the donor groups has not been thoroughly studied. The individual donor groups may be expected to surround the cations in different ways on variation of pH in a particular metal-ligand ratio due to difference in their coordination tendency including their position in the molecule to form a strong chelate as previously experienced by Motekaitis and Martell⁴ in the study of some multideanate ligand complexes. Similarly, a variation in metal-ligand ratio may also affect the mode of coordination resulting the formation of new unexpected useful complex species.

Thus, complexation reactions of the polydentate ligand BPR, involving the bivalent metal ions Ni, Cu, Zn, Pd and Cd and Ag¹ have been investigated at 25° ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$). The study includes informations on protonated, nonprotonated, hydroxo and binucleating species existing over a wide pH range (2.80–11.0) in mixtures containing 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 metal-ligand ratios.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constants : A weak inflection of pH vs a curve of BPR at $a = 1$ (Fig. 1) shows that proton from SO_3H group and the OH (adjacent to ketonic group) are simultaneously dissociated. Further, the sharp inflections at $a = 2$ and 3 indicate independent dissociation of other phenolic proton, i.e. the OH attached with the second ring (structure 1). The red colour of the ligand gradually turns purple (from pH = 4.40, $a = 1$) and finally violet (from pH ~ 7.85 , $a = 2$). These colour changes are due to domination of different ligand species under different pH ranges (H_4A and H_3A^- -red, H_2A^{2-} -purple, HA^{3-} -violet). The proton-ligand dissociation calculated as described earlier⁵ are given in Table 1.

Metal-ligand complexes :

1 : 1 Metal-BRP complexes : The red colour of 1 : 1, Ni^{II}-BPR mixture, appeared at initial pH value gradually changes to purple in the pH range 2.85–4.80 ($a \sim 3.0$). Finally it turns pinkish violet (from pH ~ 8.2 to 11.0). Thus, a steep inflection in the pH vs a curve at $a = 3$ (figure not shown) indicates the formation of purple NiHA⁻ complex below pH ~ 4.80 . Further, between pH ~ 8.0 and 11.0, formation of NiA²⁻ (pinkish violet) is evident from the increase in value of a . The corresponding equilibrium constant values obtained from mass and charge balance relations⁵ are given in Table 1.

Fig 1 pH vs a curves for Pd^{II}-BPR complexes, temp = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$, total initial ligand concentration = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

The colour of Cu^{II}-BPR (1 : 1) mixture gradually changes to blue at pH ~ 5.0 . However, at initial pH the colour appears as violet due to the presence of a mixture of red H_3A^- species and the small amount of the blue CuHA⁻ complex. The corresponding pH vs a curve with a steep inflection at $a = 3.0$ (pH ~ 5.0) confirms the formation of the monoprotonated complex at $a = 0$ to 3. A further colour change from blue to indigo and increase in a values

NOTE

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF METAL-BPR COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃)

Reaction		log <i>K</i>						
		H ⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Pd ²⁺	Ag ⁺	
H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	H ₃ A + H ⁺	-3.71 ± 0.01					
H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	H ₂ A + H ⁺	-4.33 ± 0.02					
H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	HA + H ⁺	-9.70 ± 0.01					
M + H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	MHA + 3H ⁺		-7.47	-6.76	-6.97	-6.89	-10.32
M + H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	MHA + 2H ⁺		-3.76	-3.05	-3.26	-3.18	-6.61
M + H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	MHA + H ⁺		0.57	1.28	1.07	1.15	-2.28
M + HA	\rightleftharpoons	MHA	10.27 ± 0.03	10.98 ± 0.07	10.77 ± 0.05	10.85 ± 0.03	7.42 ± 0.03	
M + H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	MA + 4H ⁺		-17.59	-17.13		-17.19	-20.89
M + H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	MA + 3H ⁺		-13.88	-13.42		-13.48	-17.18
M + H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	MA + 2H ⁺		-9.55	-9.09		-9.15	-12.85
M + HA	\rightleftharpoons	MA + H ⁺		0.15 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.02		0.55 ± 0.03	-3.15 ± 0.03
MHA	\rightleftharpoons	MA + H ⁺		-10.12	-10.37		-10.30	-10.57
M + 2H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA) ₂ + 6H ⁺			2.98	2.22		
M + 2H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA) ₂ + 4H ⁺			6.69	5.93		
M + 2H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA) ₂ + 2H ⁺			11.02	10.26		
M + 2HA	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA) ₂			20.72	19.96		
MHA + HA	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA) ₂			9.74 ± 0.05	9.19 ± 0.01		
M + 2H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA)A + 7H ⁺			-7.27			
M + 2H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA)A + 5H ⁺			-3.56			
M + 2H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA)A + 3H ⁺			0.77			
M + 2HA	\rightleftharpoons	M(HA)A + H ⁺			10.47 ± 0.02			
2M + H ₄ A	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A + 4H ⁺			-6.38	-8.25	-7.24	
2M + H ₃ A	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A + 3H ⁺			-2.67	-4.54	-3.53	
2M + H ₂ A	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A + 2H ⁺			1.66	-0.21	0.80	
2M + HA	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A + H ⁺			11.36 ± 0.03	9.49 ± 0.02	10.50 ± 0.03	
MHA + M	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A + H ⁺			0.38	-1.28	-0.35	
M ₂ A + OH ⁻	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A(OH)					8.35	
M ₂ A(OH) + OH ⁻	\rightleftharpoons	M ₂ A(OH) ₂					4.45	

show the dissociation of proton from the uncoordinated phenolic group of the ligand.

A gradual colour change red-purple-indigo from pH 2.8 to 4.35 ($a \sim 2.80$) in the titration mixture of the Zn^{II} system, subsequently precipitation of the mixture at pH ~ 4.8 ($a \sim 3.0$) and a steep inflection in the titration curve at $a = 3.0$, show the existence of ZnHA⁻ below pH ~ 4.8 . The indigo colour precipitate does not dissolve in the pH range 4.8–11.0, and therefore, analysis of the species existing in this range of pH could not be made.

Formation of PdHA⁻ is evident at $a = 0$ to 3 by the steep inflection in pH vs a curve (Fig.1). The colour of the reaction mixture at initial pH is violet instead of red, due to poor metal-ligand interaction at low pH value. The intensity of the colour gradually increases with the increase in the concentration of the PdHA⁻. At pH ~ 4.8 ($a = 3.0$) a dark violet colour solution is obtained. The violet colour of PdHA⁻ persists in the pH range 4.80–8.60 because of no change in a value. A further colour change from violet to blue occurs above pH ~ 8.60 (below pH ~ 11.0) where dissociation of proton from the protonated complex formed below $a = 3.0$ is expected.

Titration of the 1 : 1, Ag^I-BPR mixture shows a gradual colour change from red to magenta. The pH vs a curve of the system with a steep inflection at $a = 3.0$ indicates formation of protonated complex. The formation of the complex is also supported by aforesaid colour change in the reaction mixture in the pH range 4.0–8.5 ($a \sim 3.0$). In the range $a = 3.0$ to 3.7 the mixture again turns to brownish red.

The titration curve for Cd^{II} system is quite similar to other metal-BPR systems discussed above. From the steep inflection in the curve (figure not shown) at $a \sim 3.0$ and change in colour of mixture from red to violet, from the pH of deviation (pH ~ 4.30) of the complex curve from the ligand curve, formation of CdHA⁻ may be expected. Formation of turbidity has also been noted in the violet mixture from pH ~ 4.30 . Beyond pH ~ 8.0 ($a \sim 3.0$) the reaction mixture yields a thick indigo precipitate. At the end of the titration the precipitate settles down in the bottom leaving behind almost colourless solution. But, the turbidity and precipitate formations did not permit any calculation to evaluate exact mode of metal-ligand interactions.

Equilibrium constants for the reactions involving the formation of MHA or MA metal-ligand species follow the trend: $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Pd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ag}^{\text{I}}$.

1 : 2 Metal-BPR complexes : In the range $a = 0$ to 3, formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{HA})_2^-$ is indicated by comparison of pH vs a curves of BPR, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, metal-BPR systems (figures not shown) and in addition, by a colour change from red to blue. The pH vs a curve of 1 : 2 Cu^{II} -ligand system, deviates from the composite curve of ligand and 1 : 1 Cu^{II} -BPR systems from the pH of appearance of blue colour (pH ~3.7), and also shows a steep inflection at $a = 3.0$. Corresponding equilibrium constants evaluated using mass and charge balance relations are reported in Table 1.

No clear inference could be achieved for the existence of 1 : 2, Zn^{II} -BPR complex from the colour change in the titration mixture (red-purple-bluish violet) in the pH range 2.8–6.0. But the deviation of the pH vs a curve of 1 : 2 metal-ligand mixture from the composite pH vs a curve of the ligand and the 1 : 1 metal-ligand mixture from pH ~3.75 indicates attachment of two ligand molecules with the metal ion. The pH vs a curve for the system also shows steep inflection at $a = 3.0$. Equilibrium constant of the reactions involving the $\text{Zn}(\text{HA})_2^-$ species are given in Table 1. The bluish violet reaction mixture turns turbid at pH ~4.4. Existence of turbidity between pH ~4.4 and 11.0 did not permit further calculations. The evaluated equilibrium constant values are smaller than the corresponding Cu^{II} systems.

Information on the existence of 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes of Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Ag^{I} and Cd^{II} could not be inferred in solution under the present experimental conditions as the composite pH vs a curve of the ligand and 1 : 1, metal-BPR systems almost coincide with that of 1 : 2 metal-ligand system in each case.

2 : 1 Metal-BPR complexes : The titration curve for 2 : 1, Ni^{II} -BPR system does not favour the attachment of two Ni^{II} ions with the ligand molecule. The curve nearly coincides with that of 1 : 1 metal-ligand system at pH = 5.5–9.5. However, its slight departure below pH ~5.5 may be due to increased concentration of the NiHA^- complex. Above pH ~9.5 the reaction mixture turns turbid. Below pH ~4.5 the colour change in 2 : 1 Cu^{II} -BPR mixture is almost identical with that of 1 : 1 metal-ligand mixture. But, a weak inflection in the pH vs a curve at $a \sim 4.0$ indicates the formation of binucleating Cu_2A complex. The a value increases upto 7.0 (pH = 11.0). But the existence of indigo turbidity at pH = 4.7–11.0, did not allow further analysis of the curve. The 2 : 1 Zn^{II} -BPR mixture gradually turns to bluish violet (from red) from pH ~2.8 to 7.8 ($a = 4.0$). Also the reaction mixture appears turbid in the range 4.7–7.80 probably due to less solubility of bluish violet neutral Zn_2A complex. Beyond $a = 4.0$ the colour of the turbidity changes to indigo.

The pH vs a curve for 2 : 1 Pd^{II} -BPR system shows a very weak inflection at $a = 4.0$ (pH = 4.8) indicating Pd_2A

formation between $a = 0$ and 4. Existence of the new species is also inferred from the comparison of the colour of the three titration mixtures, ligand (red/purple); 1 : 1 Pd^{II} -BPR (violet) and 2 : 1, Pd^{II} -BPR (brown) between pH ~2.8 and 5.0. From the titration curve formation of $\text{Pd}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})^-$ and $\text{Pd}_2\text{A}(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$ is also concluded between $a = 4$ and 6 (pH ~10.10). However, the mixtures turn turbid beyond pH = 9.90. The equilibrium constants of blue hydroxo complexes (evaluated by mid-point method) and the Pd_2A are given in Table 1. The pH vs a curve of 2 : 1 Ag^{I} -BPR mixture deviates from that of 1 : 1 Ag^{I} -BPR mixture from pH ~4.0. A steep inflection in the curve at $a = 4.0$ (pH ~8.5), comparison of colours of the ligand (red/purple/violet), 1 : 1 metal-ligand mixture (red/magenta), 2 : 1 metal-ligand mixture (brown) below pH ~8.5, and existence of brown turbidity between pH ~4.0 and 11.0, indicate formation of binucleating complex. But the corresponding equilibrium constant could not be obtained due to the presence of turbidity in the entire pH range of complex formation. The 2 : 1 Cd^{II} -BPR mixture remains turbid beyond pH ~4.35 with colour change almost identical to the corresponding 1 : 1 metal-ligand mixture. The only difference observed in this system is the appearance of indigo-thick precipitate from a lower pH value (pH ~5.4). However, from the steep inflection in pH vs a curve at $a \sim 4.0$ (pH ~ 9.50) formation of Cd_2A may be expected.

The following order of association of the metal ions with their 1 : 1 metal-ligand species is concluded : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Pd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$.

Experimental

Standard solutions of 0.1306 *N* NaOH, 1.0 *M* KNO_3 and 0.0146 *N* HNO_3 (all A.R.) were prepared. Solutions (5.0×10^{-3} *M*) of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, AgNO_3 , $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all B.D.H.) and PdCl_2 (C.D.H.) were prepared and metal contents except Pd^{II} were determined by EDTA titration methods; Pd^{II} was estimated gravimetrically⁶. Aqueous solution of bromopyrogallol sulphonphthalein was prepared in alkali and the excess alkali was neutralised with HNO_3 .

Procedure : The following mixtures (i) 0.00146 *N* HNO_3 ; (ii) 5.0×10^{-4} *M* ligand + (i); (iii) 5.0×10^{-4} *M* metal ion + (ii); (iv) 2.5×10^{-4} *M* metal ion + (ii); (v) 1.0×10^{-3} *M* metal ion + (ii), were titrated against the NaOH solution, keeping the initial volume of each mixture 50 cm^3 (25°, $\mu = 0.1$ *M* KNO_3) using an EC 5652 pH-meter with combined electrode system. From the experimental data, titration curves (pH vs moles of alkali used per mole of ligand, a) were obtained and analysed as described earlier⁵ for obtained informations on metal-ligand interaction.

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